

Deliverable 5.1.1.2

ENERGY SIMULATION SOFTWARE METADATA SCHEMA
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Energy simulation software metadata schema

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General information

Summary

Following the requirements identified in D5.1.1.1 (generic and domain-specific fields, controlled vocabularies, and interoperability features), and drawing on the requirements analysis and domain model of Ferenz et al. [1], we developed *ERSmeta*. It offers:

- a core set of generic software metadata (identifiers, authorship, licensing, versioning, documentation links),
- domain-specific extensions for energy simulation (model class, mathematical method, temporal/spatial scope, sectors, and technologies), and
- explicit interoperability hooks (e.g., ORCID for contributors, ROR for institutions, SPDX for licenses, persistent identifiers and resolvable links).

ERSmeta is openly developed, versioned, and maintained to support reuse, extension, and alignment with community practices.

The schema provides a structured way to describe and categorize energy research software (ERS) and energy simulation software in particular. It is designed to be extensible, and aligned with FAIR principles.

Deliverable 5.1.1.2 within NFDI4Energy

Task Area 5 focuses on supporting interdisciplinary simulation efforts within energy system research. Measure 5.1 addresses the challenge of categorizing energy simulation software to provide more effective access, reuse, and interoperability. Deliverable 5.1.1.2 builds directly on the requirements defined in D5.1.1.1 [2] by providing the concrete metadata schema for energy simulation software. It serves as the bridge between requirement analysis and the subsequent processes of stakeholder engagement (D5.1.1.3) and registry implementation (Tasks 5.1.2 and 5.1.3).

The metadata schema and the implemented registry will be used in Measures 5.2, 5.3, and 5.4 to make the development of simulation scenarios easier by using the provided metadata. The metadata can help to choose the most suitable simulation models for a co-simulation scenario and integrate it.

Deliverable description

Introduction

After defining the requirements for an energy simulation software metadata schema in Deliverable 5.1.1.1, we surveyed available metadata schemas and software registries. To fully meet these requirements, we developed *ERSmeta*, a schema developed within the scope of NFDI4Energy to serve as the standard for energy simulation software. Details on the development are described in [3]. The schema is openly available on GitHub (<https://github.com/NFDI4Energy/ERSmeta>). *ERSmeta* provides an extensible schema for describing energy research software, structured into the categories of Identification and Provenance, Technical Characteristics, Model Characteristics, Community and Usability, and Quality and Sustainability. It also incorporates interoperability features such as persistent identifiers and connections to established vocabularies.

ERSmeta was selected as it fulfills the previously formulated requirements. It directly builds upon the qualitative study performed by Ferenz et al. [1]. The study builds a comprehensive domain model based on the analysis of 32 expert interviews, specifically addressing the information needs and requirements of energy researchers. In particular, *ERSmeta* implements the requirement categories identified such as provenance, usage, community, interfaces, and functionalities. This deliverable therefore reports on the availability of *ERSmeta* as the metadata schema for NFDI4Energy Task Area 5.1 and outlines its role as the basis for further work on stakeholder engagement and registry development.

Metadata and fulfillment of requirements

The *ERSmeta* schema directly addresses the requirements defined in Deliverable 5.1.1.1. Its design follows a structured categorisation that corresponds to the requirements discussed in earlier work (cf. Ferenz et al. 2025). In what follows, we describe in more detail how the schema fulfills these requirements.

First, the requirement for *generic metadata* is met through the category of Identification and Provenance. This part of the schema covers essential descriptive information such as software name, version, contributors and institutions, related projects, publications, and licensing. By including this information in a standardized way, *ERSmeta* supports the clear identification of software artifacts and ensures that provenance is traceable, which is essential for scientific transparency.

Second, the requirement for *domain-specific metadata* is addressed by the category Model Characteristics. This section captures energy-specific details such as sectors (e.g., electricity, heat) and technologies, and allows for the documentation of modeling paradigms (e.g. agent-based, optimization, hybrid approaches), mathematical methods employed, as well as temporal and spatial resolution. This directly supports comparability across modeling approaches and enables researchers to locate suitable tools for specific applications.

Third, the schema acknowledges the importance of *community and usability aspects*. In line with stakeholder feedback reported by Ferenz et al. (2025), *ERSmeta* incorporates elements such as links to documentation, tutorials, examples, and evidence of community interaction (e.g., issue trackers or forums). These fields improve the evaluation of the usability of software and community support, which are key selection criteria in research practice.

Fourth, requirements for *technical interoperability* are met through the category of Technical Characteristics. Here, *ERSmeta* records programming languages, software dependencies, operating system compatibility, and input/output formats. Furthermore, the schema integrates persistent identifiers (e.g. ORCID, ROR, SPDX) and encourages the use of controlled vocabularies, thereby ensuring alignment with broader metadata standards and facilitating machine-readable interoperability.

Nevertheless, while *ERSmeta* provides a solid and well-structured foundation for our work, further extensions are required to cover specific interoperability aspects relevant to energy simulation workflows, such as standardized interfaces for co-simulation or links to domain ontologies developed within

NFDI4Energy Measure 4.1. These additions will enhance its capacity to represent complex simulation environments and ensure seamless integration with emerging FAIR infrastructures.

Fifth, the requirement for *Quality and Sustainability* is reflected by including information on validation and testing, licensing models, release cycles, and maintenance strategies. Such metadata elements enable users to evaluate the maturity and long-term sustainability of software packages, addressing a key concern identified in interviews with the research community.

Although modularity was a stated requirement in D 5.1.1.1 [2], the current *ERSmeta* specification does not yet provide built-in mechanisms for the modular composition of metadata blocks. As an interim workaround, we recommend mask-based filtering techniques (e.g., view-profiles or "mask" features used in other registries) that allow users to hide or expose selected sections of the metadata depending on the use case. For example, JSON Schema composition keywords such as `allOf` and `anyOf` can enable the reuse and controlled combination of schema modules (JSON Schema Organization, 2020; JSON Schema Organization, 2025).

Overall, these categories demonstrate that *ERSmeta* not only satisfies the abstract requirements formulated in D5.1.1.1 but also follows requirements defined by other researchers. By covering provenance, domain specificity, community engagement, technical interoperability, and quality assurance, *ERSmeta* provides a comprehensive framework that advances the FAIR principles for energy research software. This alignment illustrates that the schema is well-suited to support the development of registries and stakeholder processes in subsequent tasks of NFDI4Energy.

Conclusion

In this deliverable, we presented *ERSmeta* as the selected metadata schema for the description of energy simulation software within NFDI4Energy Task Area 5. By adopting and extending this open schema, we address the comprehensive set of requirements defined in Deliverable 5.1.1.1 and the domain-specific needs identified by Ferez et al. [1]. *ERSmeta* balances generic software identification with the granular details required for energy systems analysis, such as temporal resolution, spatial scope, and mathematical modeling paradigms.

The adoption of *ERSmeta* provides a standardized foundation to enhance the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR) of energy research software. By incorporating persistent identifiers (ORCID, ROR) and controlled vocabularies, the schema ensures that simulation tools are not only human-readable but also machine-actionable, facilitating their integration into automated workflows and larger research data infrastructures.

This metadata schema serves as the technical cornerstone for the subsequent activities in Measure 5.1. The immediate next steps focus on the practical implementation of the software registry (Task 5.1.2) and the validation of the schema through active stakeholder engagement (Deliverable 5.1.1.3). Feedback gathered during these processes will be used to iteratively refine *ERSmeta*, ensuring it remains a living standard that evolves with the requirements of the energy research community. Ultimately, the schema and the resulting registry will enable the scenario development workflows planned in Measures 5.2, 5.3, and 5.4, thereby supporting interdisciplinary collaboration across the energy sector.

References

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